

Data Product Development for Modeling Benthic Carbon Processes in the Arctic

2 & 8 October 2025

REPORT

Online workshop “Data Product Development for Modeling Benthic Carbon Processes in the Arctic”

The workshop was organised by the EU-funded BioEcoOcean project in collaboration with EU-funded projects POMP, SEA-Quester and NECCTON. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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Workshop Overview

The workshop “Data Product Development for Modelling Benthic Carbon Processes in the Arctic” was held online on 8th and 10th October 2025. It was organised by the EU-funded BioEcoOcean project in collaboration with EU funded projects POMP, SEA-Quester and NECCTON. The workshop gathered experts in Arctic marine biogeochemistry, benthic ecology, and modeling to identify gaps and develop a roadmap for generating benthic carbon data products suitable for model applications. The event consisted of two 3-hour online sessions combining plenary discussions and collaborative group work using Miro boards. In total 30 participants from 15 countries and 20 institutions attended.

The following **objectives** were set for the workshop participants:

- Discuss current and potential methodologies and needs for utilizing benthic data in environmental models
- Review and establish clear criteria for developing data products according to the needs of both modelers and observers
- Recommend guidelines for optimized sampling designs based on the agreed data product requirements

Prior to the workshop the Organizing Committee set the following **expected outcomes**:

- List of priority data products needed by the modelers and observers
- Inventory of relevant datasets and databases
- Roadmap towards developing benthic carbon data products
- Recommendations for optimized sampling designs

The workshop concluded with comprehensive results contributing to the first three outcomes, with limited input to the fourth expected outcomes. All workshop outcomes will be summarized in a peer-reviewed publication to be submitted to an international journal in 2026.

Pre-workshop survey

Before the online meeting, all registered participants were invited to complete an initial survey. The questionnaire aimed to identify key data needs and evaluate the relevance of existing and emerging data products for improving our understanding and modeling benthic carbon cycling in the Arctic Ocean.

The survey consisted of two main sections. In the first section, respondents evaluated a proposed list of **7 scientific variables related to benthic organic carbon** in terms of their relevance, as well as current and expected readiness of each as a data product. The list of potential variables related to benthic carbon processing was selected by experts attending the workshop on "*Biogenic Data Products to Advance Ocean Carbon Sequestration Modelling in the Arctic*" organized jointly by EU projects EU4OceanObs and ECOTIP. The proposed variables were also specified in the "*Technical specification of the benthic products*" prepared by participants of the workshop organized by the EU NECCTON project "*New Copernicus Capability for Trophic Ocean Networks*". In the second section,

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respondents were asked about their opinion on a **set of common challenges in modeling benthic carbon cycling in the Arctic Ocean**.

In total 18 responses were collected. Initial results of this survey were presented to participants during the workshop as a starting point for discussions, and will also be further analyzed in the forthcoming manuscript.

Summary of Day 1

Session 1: From measurements to state variables - finding the way to data products

The objective of the first session was to verify the needs and priorities for benthic carbon data products. The summary of the initial survey results was presented together with a common agreement on definitions. All participants were invited to an interactive exercise the aim of which was to identify common links and existing gaps between empirical measurements of the benthic environment (experimental and field) made by observers, and variables obtained by modelers in the modeling approaches they use.

After identifying the common set of measurements and variables of interest, participants were invited to discuss:

- Where do measurements and model variables align?
- Where are the critical gaps?
- How could we better reconcile the existing efforts to maximize impact?

During this exercise almost 90 different thoughts, reflections and questions were gathered. The initial analysis of results allowed us to identify four different contextual groups related to **environmental/biological properties, stocks, fluxes/rates, and relations of interest**.

	property	stock	flux/rate
measurements	functional traits	community composition, food web	respiration, nutrients
observers needs	habitat type	TOC	Secondary production
modeled variables		POC/TOC, macrobenthos	remineralisation, sedimentation, resuspension
modellers needs	functional traits, OM quality		carbon flux & burial

Figure 1: Summary of ideas gathered from the collaborative exercise during session 1 aiming to identify common links and existing gaps between measurements and modeled variables.

Of the many relations of interests mentioned, the most common concerned the evaluation of microbial, meiofaunal and macrofaunal contributions to fluxes as well as increase of complexity in the measured/modeled processes. The exercise allowed us to determine and add two more scientific variables to the list proposed in the initial survey, namely “**benthic functional traits**” and “**benthic nutrients**”.

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Figure 2: A snapshot of verified (blue) and emerging (red) scientific variables related to benthic carbon that were discussed or identified during the workshop.

Summary of Day 2

The second day of the workshop was organised around three thematic sessions intended to obtain a comprehensive list of existing benthic carbon data products according to the knowledge of the participating experts. We defined various levels of data products according to the criteria proposed by Webb et al. (2025; 10.1016/j.marpol.2024.106578).

Figure 3: Diagram representing data organisation levels (copied from Webb et al., 2025)

Session II: What data products are already out there?

The aim of Session II was to:

- identify existing databases and other sources of data corresponding to the nine selected scientific variables describing benthic carbon processes, and
- estimate the corresponding level of data product development

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Jointly, participants identified almost 70 data sources, largely considered to be L3 and L4 data products. Data which can be considered as L1 or L2 was purposefully left out of the exercise. Further screening and analysis of this “sources database” will be conducted during the manuscript preparation phase.

Session III: Where are we heading?

During the next exercise, participants discussed and assessed the data product maturity levels of benthic carbon variables and proposed recommendations and roadmaps for their development. For variables at higher maturity levels, expert groups also aimed to outline actions for developing and ensuring quality control criteria. Built upon the initial survey, this exercise aimed to set the goals for developing and advancing data products associated with the selected variables.

Building on insights from previous sessions, these discussions provided a clearer picture of where progress has been made and where further development is needed. Experts highlighted large variability in data maturity among benthic carbon variables, with most requiring improved standardization, better spatial and temporal coverage, and more long-term observations. Several comments pointed to the need for harmonizing measurement units, improving data accessibility, and expanding Arctic-specific observations, particularly for bioturbation, benthic flora and sediment oxygen consumption. For more mature variables, experts emphasized the importance of establishing quality control criteria and ensuring long-term data continuity.

Session IV: How to optimize the sampling designs?

The last session of the workshop discussed how to transform the outcomes of the workshop into specific actions, realized either through any of the organizing projects or by the community at large. To guide the conversation we referred back to the example relations of interest from Day 1 such as:

- From the modeler’s perspective:
 - Evaluation of microbial, meiofaunal and macrofaunal contributions to fluxes;
 - Natural rates of resuspension and carbon remineralization during those events.
- From the observer’s perspective:
 - Inclusion of natural variability – move beyond using mean values;
 - Partitioning of process rates by functional groups.

This format stimulated the group to search for ways to better include the modelers' needs in sampling efforts, and promote the use of models to answer questions raised by observers, thus contributing to the final workshop objective.

Evaluation survey

The workshop concluded with an evaluation survey to which 11 participants responded. Overall, participants appreciated the interactive and collaborative format of the workshop the most. They valued the diverse participation of experts from different disciplines, the clearly set goals, as well as the good organization and effective facilitation. Respondents also highlighted the value of the workshop as a knowledge sharing platform and an opportunity to connect modelers with observers. On the other hand, it was pointed out that the representation of the modelling community could have been broadened, and that follow-up actions were made clearer. While the use of online collaborative boards is seen as engaging and effective by most, some found it distracting or difficult to navigate. This constructive feedback provides excellent recommendations for improving future

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workshops which aim to meet similar objectives but on different topics and/or engaging different communities.

Acknowledgements

We thank all the workshop participants for their active engagement and valuable contributions throughout the discussions and exercises, and willingness to participate in the pre-workshop survey. This workshop is a contribution to the Marine Organic Carbon Atlas Living Lab of the EU BioEcoOcean project and to the activities of collaborating EU projects: SeaQvester, POMP and NECCTON.

Workshop Organizing Committee

Marta Szczepanek, Monika Kędra, Artur Palacz, Dominik Krzysiński - Institute of Oceanology Polish Academy of Sciences, Poland (EU BioEcoOcean, EU SeaQester)

Bodil Bluhm - UiT Arctic University of Norway, Norway (EU POMP)

Jennifer Dannheim - Alfred Wegener Institute, Germany (EU POMP)

Marilaure Gregoire - University of Liège, Belgium (EU NECCTON)

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Appendix 1

Workshop Agenda

Day 1: 2 October 2025, 12:00-15:00 UTC. [See what time it is for you](#)

Join Zoom Meeting: <https://us06web.zoom.us/j/82253296868?pwd=45v8ilXvIV0dNIDchQaa6bgzW57Do1.1>

Meeting ID: 822 5329 6868, Passcode: 239911

- | | |
|-----------------|--|
| 12:00–12:10 UTC | Welcome and what are we here for? [Marta Szczepanek] |
| 12:10–12:30 UTC | Tour de Table [All participants] |
| 12:30–12:40 UTC | Workshop rationale [Organizing Committee] |
| 12:40–12:50 UTC | The modelling perspective [Cristina Schulz] |
| 12:50–13:30 UTC | Session I: From measurements to state variables - finding the way to data products <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Introduction and review of survey results [Marta Szczepanek]• Brief tutorial on Miro.com [Marta Szczepanek]• Interactive work and discussions using Miro boards [All participants] |
| 13:30–13:40 UTC | <i>Break</i> |
| 13:40–14:40 UTC | Session I (continued) - From measurements to state variables - finding the way to data products <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Group work and plenary discussions using Miro boards• Expected outcome: List of priority data products needed by the modellers and observers |
| 14:40–15:00 UTC | Wrap-up of Day 1 and presentation of Objectives for Day 2 |

Day 2: 8 October 2025, 13:00-16:00 UTC. [See what time it is for you](#)

Join Zoom Meeting: <https://us06web.zoom.us/j/84158686804?pwd=OuApFauftpS6iQhJyflPlrPOXoU8pU.1>

Meeting ID: 841 5868 6804, Passcode: 973669

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- 13:00–13:15 UTC** **Recap of Day 1 and Introduction to Day 2** [Marta Szczepanek]
- 13:15–13:30 UTC** **Example of existing data product developments: CASCADE** [Örjan Gustafsson, TBC]
- 13:30–14:15 UTC** **Session II: What data products are already out there?**
- Group work and plenary discussions using Miro boards
 - Expected outcome: Inventory of relevant datasets and databases
- 14:15–14:30 UTC** *Break*
- 14:30–15:20 UTC** **Session III: Where are we heading?**
- Group work and plenary discussions using Miro boards
 - Expected outcome: Roadmap towards developing benthic carbon data products
- 15:20–15:40 UTC** **Session IV: How do we optimize the sampling designs?** [Monika Kędra]
- Plenary discussion
 - Expected outcome: initial recommendations for including model needs in sampling efforts
- 15:40–15:45 UTC** **Workshop evaluation survey** [Dominik Krzyimiński]
- 15:45–16:00 UTC** **Final Discussion, Next Steps & Closing Remarks** [Organizing Committee]

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Appendix 2

List of participants

Name	Surname	Institution	Country
Łukasz	Barysz	Institute of Oceanology Polish Academy of Sciences	Poland
Bodil	Bluhm	UiT The Arctic University of Norway	Norway
James	Bradley	National Centre for Scientific Research	France
Séverine	Chevalier	University of Liège	Belgium
Lee	Cooper	University of Maryland Center for Environmental Science	USA
Jennifer	Danheim	Alfred Wegener Institute Helmholtz Center for Polar and Marine Research	Germany
Zhixuan	Feng	East China Normal University	China
Christina	Goethel	University of Maryland Center for Environmental Science	USA
Jacqueline	Grebmaier	University of Maryland Center for Environmental Science	USA
Marilaure	Grégoire	University of Liège	Netherlands
Parima	Hajjalizadeh	University of Tehran	Iran
Monika	Kędra	Institute of Oceanology Polish Academy of Sciences	Poland
Karol	Kuliński	Institute of Oceanology Polish Academy of Sciences	Poland
Dominik	Krzymiński	Institute of Oceanology Polish Academy of Sciences	Poland
Jack	Middelburg	Utrecht University	Netherlands
Hanna	Modin	UiT The Arctic University of Norway	Norway
Lina	Mtwana Nordlund	Uppsala University	Sweden
Artur	Palacz	Institute of Oceanology Polish Academy of Sciences	Poland
Christof	Pearce	Aarhus University	Denmark
Philip	Pika	Charles University in Prague	Czechia
Paul	Renaud	Akvaplan-niva	Norway
Annette	Samuelsen	Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center	Norway
Cristina	Schultz	Northeastern University	USA
Samantha	Siedlecki	University of Connecticut	USA
Marc	Silberberger	National Marine Fisheries Research Institute	Poland
Paul	Snelgrove	Memorial University	Canada
Martin	Solan	University of Southampton	UK
Marta	Szczepanek	Institute of Oceanology Polish Academy of Sciences	Poland
Anna	Törnroos-Remes	Åbo Akademi University	Finland
Amanda	Ziegler	Akvaplan-niva	Norway